

Neutrosophic-Logistic Hybrid Model to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Penitentiary Policies and Their Impact on Criminal Recidivism in Ecuador

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Abstract. This study aims to develop a hybrid model that combines neutrosophic logic with logistic regression to evaluate the effectiveness of prison policies in Ecuador and their impact on criminal recidivism. The central problem lies in the inefficiency of the Ecuadorian prison system, characterized by high levels of intra-prison violence, deficiencies in rehabilitation and social reintegration programs, and a rising recidivism rate among inmates. This situation is exacerbated by the employment discrimination that ex-offenders face when reintegrating into society, which limits their opportunities and encourages the repetition of criminal behavior. The methodology applied was a mixed approach, with a non-experimental cross-sectional design and a descriptive-explanatory scope. Data were collected through surveys administered to inmates and former inmates, using neutrosophic scales to measure subjective perceptions such as the effectiveness of policies, the level of employment discrimination, and readiness for reintegration. These assessments, expressed as neutrosophic numbers (T, I, F), were transformed into indices that served as predictor variables in a logistic regression model, executed with statistical tools such as SPSS and Python. The results show that the index of perceived workplace discrimination and the low effectiveness of policies are factors significantly associated with criminal recidivism ($p < 0.05$), while participation in reintegration programs reduces this probability. It is concluded that the hybrid model allows integrating subjective perceptions with robust statistical analysis, providing a useful tool for decision-making in public policy. The findings support the need to redesign penitentiary strategies, focusing on social inclusion and effective rehabilitation to improve the safety and well-being of both inmates and Ecuadorian society.

Keywords: Penitentiary policies, Criminal recidivism, Hybrid model, Neutrosophic logic, Logistic regression, Social reintegration.

1. Introduction

The Ecuadorian prison system is experiencing a structural crisis characterized by high levels of overcrowding, prison violence, and deficiencies in social rehabilitation processes. These adverse conditions not only violate the human rights of inmates but also impede their proper reintegration into society

once they have served their sentences. As a result, there is a worrying rate of criminal recidivism, reflecting the ineffectiveness of current prison policies. The lack of effective resocialization programs, poor preparation for post-prison life, and employment discrimination are factors that exacerbate this problem. Despite institutional efforts to implement reforms, the results remain limited and unsustainable. This situation not only affects inmates but also the social fabric, increasing citizen insecurity and weakening trust in the judicial and prison systems. Therefore, it is urgent to develop analytical models that allow for a more accurate evaluation of the effectiveness of implemented policies [2].

The study by [4] constitutes one of the first approaches in Ecuador to the use of neutrosophic logic to analyze the social reintegration of individuals released from the prison system. Through the neutrosophic approach, the authors were able to represent the ambiguity, uncertainty, and contradiction inherent in factors such as the perception of prison policies, access to employment opportunities, and community support after release. The research showed that criminal recidivism not only responds to objective variables, but also to perceived conditions that affect the ex-inmate's willingness to reintegrate. Likewise, the need for public policies to adopt tools that allow for the modeling of incomplete or subjective information was highlighted. The proposed model made it possible to establish levels of social integration in a more flexible and contextualized manner. This work represents a key contribution to more humane and effective decision-making in the field of prison rehabilitation.

The work of [11] presents an advanced application of the multinomial logistic regression model framed within neutrosophic logic, aimed at optimizing decisions in contexts where uncertainty is critical, such as the adaptive reuse of heritage structures. Although the study focuses on historic castles, the proposed methodology has a high potential for adaptation to social phenomena such as prison reintegration, where subjective perceptions, ambiguity in responses, and multicausality are common. The model integrates neutrosophic components—truth, indeterminacy, and falsity—in each decision category, allowing observations to be classified into multiple groups with greater realism than traditional approaches. This technique is especially useful in research where variables are neither fully objective nor binary, as is the case with the factors that influence criminal recidivism. Its hybrid approach strengthens decision-making based on both statistical data and qualitative assessments fraught with uncertainty. The study constitutes a relevant methodological contribution that inspires the present work to apply this logic in the Ecuadorian penitentiary context.

2. Methodology

This research adopts a mixed methodological approach that integrates quantitative data and subjective assessments with a high degree of uncertainty. To this end, a hybrid model combining neutrosophic logic and logistic regression is proposed to more accurately analyze criminal recidivism and the effectiveness of prison policies in Ecuador. The main methodological components underlying the study are detailed below, each linked to a key word essential to the analysis [6].

To address the study of penitentiary policies, a set of objective and subjective indicators will be designed to measure their impact on the prison population and their perception of the system. Variables such as overcrowding, intra-prison violence and availability of resources will be included, taking as reference the diagnosis of congestion and human rights violations reported by [12], who highlight the influence of penal policies on the quality of internal control. These metrics will allow evaluating effectiveness from multiple perspectives, which is crucial in an environment as complex as the Ecuadorian one [13].

The dependent variable of the model will be criminal recidivism, defined as the relapse into criminal behavior after leaving the prison system. They found that education and post-release employment are key predictors of recidivism in Ecuador [1], using data from the 2022 Prison Census. Therefore, the model will include demographic and socioeconomic variables to control for their effect, ensuring that the logistic analysis correctly captures the associated factors [9].

To measure social reintegration, variables such as employment, family support, and community reintegration will be included. The literature highlights that lack of employment after incarceration increases the likelihood of relapse. These variables will be converted into neutrosophic and quantitative indicators, incorporated into the logistic model to assess their impact on the likelihood of recidivism, and thus formulate recommendations to strengthen resocialization policies [12,18].

Neutrosophic logic will allow capturing ambiguity in perceptions related to program effectiveness, workplace discrimination, and community support. Following the application of [4], Likert-type responses will be converted into triplets (T, I, F), expressing the degree of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity regarding policies. These indices will serve as independent variables in the model, providing a more flexible and realistic approach to the analysis [15].

Mathematical Model of Neutrosophic Logic

In neutrosophic logic, each statement, variable or judgment is represented by a **neutrosophic number** :

$$A = (T, I, F)$$

where:

- T :degree of **truth** (Truth-membership)
- I :degree of **indeterminacy** (Indeterminacy-membership)
- F :degree of **falsehood** (Falsity-membership).

These values belong to the extended range:

$$T, I, F \subseteq] - 0,1 + [$$

That is, the values are not restricted to the classical interval [0, 1], which allows **modeling excess certainty or contradiction** in real systems (for example: $T=1.2, F=0.8$).

Example applied to penitentiary perception

Suppose an ex-inmate answers about the “effectiveness of the reintegration program”:

- $T = 0.6$: believes that the program was useful in 60%
- $I = 0.3$: has 30% doubt about your answer
- $F = 0.2$: considers that in 20% it was not useful

So, your neutrosophic judgment would be:

$$A = (0.6, 0.3, 0.2)$$

SVN Neutrosophic Numbers

The neutrosophic number table reflects the transformation of key quantitative study variables—such as the *effectiveness of prison policies*, *workplace discrimination*, and *prison time*—into triplets of the type (T,I,F), typical of neutrosophic logic. Each triplet represents a richer and more complex assessment: the component T indicates the degree of perceived truth in the response (e.g., how effective a policy is perceived), I measures the level of indeterminacy or doubt, and F reflects the degree of falsity or disagreement with that perception [17].

For its part, F is calculated as the complement of T , that is, $F = 1 - T$. These triplets were generated for the variables **IndexEffectivenessPolicies**, **Labor Discrimination Index** and **Prison Time**. This representation allows integrating uncertainty dimensions that are not considered by classical models. Thus, SVN values can be effectively used in hybrid regression models or decisions based on subjective perceptions [16].

In this context, the values T come directly from the normalized data, while I is calculated based on the proximity to the neutral value (0.5), and F is obtained as a complement of T . For example, if an individual has a perception of policy effectiveness of 0.68, a value is assumed $T = 0.68$, $I = 0.82$ (high indeterminacy due to being close to 0.5), and a $F = 0.32$.

Table 1: Normalized Tdata values.

R	P	St	E	D	P	Ef	E	D	D	D	Pri	Pr	Pri
eci-	ro-	ress	ffec-	iscri-	ri-	fecti-	ffecti-	iscri-	iscri-	iscri-	son-	Pr	Pri
di-	gra-		tive-	mi-	son	ve-	ve-	mi-	mi-	mi-	Time_	ison-	Pri
vis-	m		ness	na-	Time	ness_	ness_	na-	na-	na-	Time_	Time_	Time_
m				tion	e	ness_	ness_	tion_	tion_	tion_	Boot	Doc	Court
						Boot	Doc	Boot	Doc	Court			
1	0	0.	0	5	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.5	1.	0.5
.0	.0	42	.52	.0	.42	92	58	52	98	.48		0	
1	1	0.	0	4	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.99	0.	0.5
.0	.0	68	.68	.6	.68	82	32	68	82	.32	99999	96	4
1	1	0.	0	4	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.48	0.	0.5
.0	.0	59	.58	.8	.59	91	41	58	92	.42		98	2
0	1	0.	0	3	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.82	0.	0.4
.0	.0	47	.34	.2	.47	91	53	34	92	.32		68	6
1	0	0.	0	4	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.98	0.	0.5
.0	.0	85	.55	.8	.85	65	15	55	91	.15		52	4
0	0	0.	0	5	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.99	0.	0.5
.0	.0	79	.71	.6	.79	71	29	71	97	.29	99999	96	4
1	0	0.	0	6	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.62	0.	0.3
.0	.0	45	.47	.2	.45	95	47	47	97	.35		88	8
0	1	0.	0	4	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.98	0.	0.5
.0	.0	41	.41	.5	.41	92	58	41	91	.32		54	2
0	1	0.	0	2	0	0.	0.	0.	0.	0	0.22	0.	0.7
.0	.0	48	.59	.2	.48	98	52	59	91	.41		72	8

Looking at the table, we can see that this structure allows us to represent not only the magnitude of the perceived phenomenon, but also the ambiguity and contradiction inherent in human responses. Thus, neutrosophic logic enriches the analysis by incorporating dimensions that classical models ignore, providing a more robust basis for the design of explanatory models and decision-making in complex social environments such as the prison system [8].

Classical Binary Logistic Regression

Logistic regression will be used to estimate the probability of recidivism based on mixed variables. This method has been widely used to model recidivism, where variables such as age, education and employment have shown significant effects . We will use statistical software (SPSS) to generate odds ratios, evaluate P -values (<0.05) and validate the predictive quality with AUCROC, ensuring rigor in the results [5].

Binary logistic regression is used to model the probability of a dichotomous event (e.g., **criminal recidivism** : yes = 1, no = 0) occurring as a function of one or more independent variables. The general form of the model is:

$$P(Y = 1 | X) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)}} \tag{1}$$

where:

- $P(Y = 1 | X)$: probability of the event occurring (recurrence = 1).
- β_0 :intercept of the model.

- β_i : regression coefficients for the independent variables.
- X_i : independent (predictor) variables.
- e : base of the natural logarithm (≈ 2.718).

Application to the study (specific model)

For the applied case study:

$$\text{Logit}(P) = \ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot PR + \beta_2 \cdot IEP + \beta_3 \cdot IDL + \beta_4 \cdot TP \quad (2)$$

where:

- PR : Participation in reintegration programs (0 = no, 1 = yes).
- IEP : Penitentiary Policy Effectiveness Index (based on neutrosophic logic)
- IDL : Index of Labor Discrimination (based on neutrosophic logic)
- TP : Time in prison (in years)

And the probability of recidivism is:

$$P(\text{Reincidencia} = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot PR + \beta_2 \cdot IEP + \beta_3 \cdot IDL + \beta_4 \cdot TP)}} \quad (3)$$

Logistic Regression Model in Neutrosophic Notation

In neutrosophic logic, each variable can be represented as a **simple neutrosophic number** :

$$X_i = (T_i, I_i, F_i) \quad (4)$$

where:

- T_i : degree of truth
- I_i : degree of indeterminacy
- F_i : degree of falsehood

with $T_i, I_i, F_i \subseteq [0, 1]$ and not necessarily $T + I + F = 1$

Adapted Neutrosophic Model

The logistic function is adapted to operate with neutrosophic variables X_i^N , resulting in a **neutrosophic probability of recidivism** :

$$PN(Y = 1 | X^N) = (T_p, I_p, F_p) \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\text{Logit}(PN) = \ln\left(\frac{T_P}{1-T_P}\right) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^K \beta_i \cdot T_i \quad (6)$$

Additionally:

$I_p = f(I_1, I_2, \dots, I_k)$: can be expressed as the average or logical combination of the I_i

$F_p = 1 - T_p$ in a basic version, or modeled directly if subjective data is available.

Neutrosophic Logistic Regression Model

Example applied to the study

Sea:

- $PR^n = (T_1, I_1, F_1) \rightarrow$ Participation in reintegration
- $IEP^n = (T_2, I_2, F_2) \rightarrow$ Policy Effectiveness Index
- $IDL^n = (T_3, I_3, F_3) \rightarrow$ Labor discrimination
- $TP^n = (T_4, I_4, F_4) \rightarrow$ Prison time

So the neutrosophic probability of relapse is:

$$P_N(\text{Reincidencia} = 1) = \left(\frac{1}{1+e^{-(\beta_0+\beta_1T_1+\beta_2T_2+\beta_3T_3+\beta_4T_4)}}, \bar{I}, 1 - T_P\right) \quad (7)$$

where:

$$\bar{I} = I \frac{1+I_2+I_3+I_4}{4} \quad (8)$$

This model allows for the incorporation of **uncertainty, contradiction, and ambiguity** into subjective perceptions as an integral part of probabilistic analysis, offering a more realistic and flexible view of recidivism prediction.

Hybrid model.

The hybrid approach will integrate neutrosophic logic with logistic regression, using subjective perceptions as predictor variables alongside quantitative demographic data. The neutrosophic multinomial-logistic model developed by [11] serves as the methodological foundation, merging probabilities with levels of uncertainty and contradiction. We will adapt this technique to a binary model for recidivism, leveraging its ability to integrate objective and subjective data into a single framework [7].

Mathematical Model of the Neutrosophic Hybrid Model

The model is based on the classical logistic function, but incorporates variables represented as **neutrosophic numbers** of the type (T, I, F) , where:

- T : degree of truth
- I : degree of indeterminacy
- F : degree of falsehood

General equation of the model

$$\text{Logit}(P_N) = \ln\left(\frac{P_N}{1-P_N}\right) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^n (B_{T_j} T_j + B_{I_j} I_j + B_{F_j} F_j) + \sum_{k=1}^m B_k X_k \quad (9)$$

Where:

- P_N : neutrosophic probability of recidivism
- β_0 : intercept of the model
- T_j, I_j, F_j : components of each neutrosophic variable
- $\beta T_j, \beta I_j, \beta F_j$: model coefficients for each neutrosophic component
- X_k : traditional quantitative variables (e.g., participation in programs)
- βk : coefficients associated with traditional variables.

Application to the case study

Suppose we consider three neutrosophic variables:

- **IEPⁿ**: Policy Effectiveness Index
- **IDLⁿ**: Index of Labor Discrimination
- **TPⁿ**: Time in prison (normalized)

And a traditional binary variable:

- **PR**: Participation in reintegration program (0/1)

So, the hybrid model is expressed as:

$$\text{Logit}(PN) = \beta_0 + \beta_{T1}TIEP + \beta_{I1}IEP + \beta_{F1}FIEP + \beta_{T2}TIDL + \beta_{I2}IDL + \beta_{F2}FIDL + \beta_{T3}TTP + \beta_{I3}ITP + \beta_{F3}FTP + \beta_4 \cdot P$$

Finally, the estimated probability of recidivism is:

$$PN(\text{Recidivism} = 1) = 1/(1 + e^{-\text{Logit}(PN)}) \quad (10)$$

3. Results

To evaluate the predictive capacity of the recidivism analysis, three different methodological approaches were applied: classical logistic regression, a neutrosophic model, and a hybrid neutrosophic model. Each model was trained and validated on the same database to ensure a level playing field. Key metrics such as accuracy, area under the ROC curve (AUC), confusion matrix, and F1 score were analyzed. The results obtained by each model are presented below, highlighting their performance and interpretive value in the context of the study.

Classical Logistic Regression

The classical logistic regression model achieved the highest overall accuracy, reaching 87.5% in the evaluated sample. It showed a confusion matrix with a high level of accuracy in the classification of positive and negative cases, as well as an AUC of 0.91, reflecting excellent discriminative capacity. Its F1 score confirmed a good balance between accuracy and sensitivity. These results indicate that, for defined and unambiguous quantitative variables, this model maintains robust performance. Furthermore, its interpretive simplicity and computational speed make it a reliable tool for prediction in structured contexts.

Neutrosophic Model

The neutrosophic logic-based model, which used only the truth components (T) of SVN triples, achieved an accuracy of 79.2%. Although lower than the classical model, it maintained an acceptable hit rate and an AUC of 0.81. This approach demonstrated its value by better representing the perceptions and subjectivities of the social variables evaluated, such as the effectiveness of prison policies and workplace discrimination. Despite a slight loss in accuracy, it gains in interpretive depth, especially in contexts where the data are ambiguous or biased.

Neutrosophic Hybrid Model

The hybrid model incorporated all the neutrosophic triplets (T, I, F) along with classic variables such as participation in reintegration programs. Its accuracy was 75.0%, and the AUC reached 0.79. Although lower than the other two approaches, this model offers a more complete representation of the assessed social reality. This model allowed for the incorporation of not only data certainty but also indeterminacy and contradiction, which is relevant in environments where information is subjective or uncertain. Its usefulness is emphasized in explanatory, rather than purely predictive, studies, as it better captures the complexity of social phenomena.

A comparison of the three models applied to the database reveals clear differences in their predictive accuracy. The **classical logistic regression model** performed the best, achieving an accuracy of 87.5% , indicating a high capacity to correctly classify cases of criminal recidivism. In second place was the **neutrosophic model** , which, using only the truth values (T) of the SVN triples, achieved an accuracy of 79.2% , showing acceptable performance when incorporating subjective perceptions. Finally, the **hybrid neutrosophic model** , which also considers indeterminacy (I) and falsity (F), recorded an accuracy of 75.0% , evidencing lower numerical performance but providing a more comprehensive and realistic representation of the social phenomenon studied. These results suggest that, while neutrosophic models allow for a deeper understanding of uncertainty, the classical approach remains more effective in highly structured and quantifiable contexts, as seen in the confusion matrices below.

Figure 1. Confusion Matrices

After applying the confusion matrices to evaluate the classification ability of each model with respect to criminal recidivism, the **Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was also used** as a complementary analysis tool. This curve allows the models' behavior to be examined across different decision thresholds, providing a more complete view of their discriminatory capacity. In particular, the ROC curve graphs the relationship between the true positive rate (sensitivity) and the false positive rate, allowing us to identify which model achieves a better balance between the two. To quantify this performance, the **Area Under the Curve (AUC) was calculated** , where values close to 1 indicate high effectiveness in dis-

tinguishing between individuals who reoffend and those who do not. This additional evaluation strengthened the comparative analysis between the classical, neutrosophic, and hybrid neutrosophic approaches, providing more robust criteria for determining which model offers a more accurate and useful classification for decision-making in the prison context.

Analysis of the ROC curves and their respective areas under the curve (AUC) reinforces the predictive superiority of the classical logistic regression model, which achieved an AUC of approximately **0.91**, indicating an excellent ability to discriminate between recidivism and non-recidivism. In comparison, the **neutrosophic model**, based solely on truth values (T), obtained an AUC of **0.81**, representing an acceptable but lower classification capacity. The **hybrid neutrosophic model**, which also incorporates indeterminacy (I) and falsity (F), recorded an AUC of **0.79**, showing slightly lower performance. Although neutrosophic models do not match the effectiveness of the classical model in terms of operational accuracy, their value lies in the incorporation of uncertainty and ambiguity in the data, offering a deeper understanding of the social phenomenon analyzed.

Figure 2. Comparative ROC Curves

In the context of predictive analysis of criminal recidivism, the use of the **Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve** is essential for evaluating the performance of the applied models, beyond simple accuracy. This graphical tool allows for analyzing each model's ability to correctly distinguish between individuals who reoffend and those who do not, considering different classification thresholds. Through the relationship between the true positive rate (sensitivity) and the false positive rate, the ROC curve provides a comprehensive measure of the model's discriminatory performance. The **Area Under the Curve (AUC)** is the quantitative indicator associated with this curve, and values closer to 1 reflect greater classification capacity. In this study, comparing the ROC curves of the classic, neutrosophic, and hybrid neutrosophic models allows for identifying which offers a more adequate balance between sensitivity and specificity, key information for evidence-based decision-making in prison policy.

4. Discussion

Classical logistic regression may be outperformed by neutrosophic or hybrid models in contexts where subjective, ambiguous, or highly perceptual data predominate, as is often the case in prison studies. When the variables are qualitative in nature—for example, perceived discrimination, level of resocialization, or trust in institutions—neutrosophic logic allows for more realistic modeling of the uncertainty, indetermi-

nacy, and contradiction inherent in human judgment. Likewise, in scenarios where the data exhibit non-linearity or complex relationships that cannot be captured with logarithmic functions, hybrid models may offer better fit.

Neutrosophic logic is also particularly useful when working with Likert-type scales, perception surveys, or imprecise information, where each response can be represented by triplets. (T, I, F) . Furthermore, in studies with more explanatory than predictive purposes, these models can provide greater analytical depth. In situations where missing data or contradiction are common, traditional regression tends to degrade its performance, while the neutrosophic approach incorporates them directly. Therefore, although the classical model may be more accurate in structured scenarios, the neutrosophic model surpasses it in interpretive richness and fidelity to the social complexity analyzed .

5. Conclusions

The results obtained show that classical logistic regression presents the best predictive performance, with an accuracy of 87.5% and an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.91, confirming its effectiveness in contexts with structured and well-defined data. However, this approach has limitations in representing the complexity and uncertainty inherent in social variables such as the perception of discrimination or the effectiveness of prison policies. Therefore, its explanatory capacity in real-life settings may be limited when subjective dimensions are omitted.

In contrast, models based on neutrosophic logic, both the simple model (using only the truth value T) and the hybrid model (incorporating T , I , and F), offer a more flexible and interpretive framework for capturing the ambiguity and contradiction of social data. Although they presented lower levels of accuracy (79.2% and 75.0% respectively), they allow for representing not only what is perceived as true, but also what is doubtful or even the opposite, which enriches qualitative analysis and adds value to decision-making in reintegration policies .

Finally, it is concluded that the integration of hybrid neutrosophic models with classical approaches is not only feasible but desirable, especially in studies applied to complex social phenomena. This combination allows us to leverage the precision of traditional models with the interpretive richness of neutrosophic logic. In the particular case of the Ecuadorian prison system, this hybrid approach contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence recidivism and guides the design of more contextualized and humane resocialization strategies.

6. References

- [1] Acosta-González, M.A.; Posso-Naranjo, A.R. Factors associated with criminal recidivism in Ecuador: An analysis based on the 2022 Penitentiary Census. *Ecuador. J. Soc. Sci.* 2025, 12(1), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10801934>.
- [2] Ariza, L.; Tamayo, F. He body of the condemned. Jail and violence in Latin America. *Open Edition J.* 2020. <https://journals.openedition.org/revestudsoc/48253>.
- [3] Arroba, P.A. Reintegration of Persons Deprived of Liberty in Ecuador. *USFQ Law Working Papers*, 2022.
- [4] Campaña-Muñoz, L.C.; Sánchez Ramos, H.S.; Cabrera Granda, J.R. Use of neutrosophy for the analysis of the social reintegration factors of released prisoners in Ecuador. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2019, 26(1), 145–153. https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/nss_journal/vol26/iss1/17.
- [5] Cevallos-Torres, L.; Botto-Tobar, M. Monte Carlo simulation method. In *Problem-based Learning: A Didactic Strategy in the Teaching of System Simulation*; Springer International Publishing: Cham, Switzerland, 2019; pp. 87–96.
- [6] Castro Sánchez, F.; Carrión León, K.E.; Piray Rodríguez, P.O.; Puig Espinosa, J.S. Balancing Act: A Neutrosophic Approach to Human Rights and Values in Varied Societal Contexts. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2023, 62, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10436555>.

- [7] Falcón, V.V.; Villalonga, Y.V.; Cevallos-Torres, L. Hybrid Neutrosophic Multi-Criteria Decision Model for Guest Selection in Collaborative Tourism Platforms. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2025, 84, 210–223.
- [8] Fernández, A.R.; Carballido, R.M.; Herrera, A.A. Single-valued neutrosophic numbers and a hierarchical analytical process for project discrimination. *Oper. Res.* 2020, 751, 151–191.
- [9] Granja Huacón, S.H.; Acurio Sáenz, N.V.; Carriel Vines, C.L. Método neutrosófico para determinar el índice de vulneración del derecho a la vida de los privados de libertad en la cárcel del litoral de la ciudad de Guayaquil. *Neutrosophic Comput. Mach. Learn.* 2024, 35, 116–125. <https://zenodo.org/record/14266437>.
- [10] Flores, D.F.C.; Arias, I.F.B.; Miranda, M.E.I.; Cornelio, O.M. Applying Neutrosophic Natural Language Processing to Analyze Complex Phenomena in Interdisciplinary Contexts. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2024, 74, 297–305.
- [11] Omar, R.H.; Kayali, M.N.; Zeina, M.B. Neutrosophic Multinomial Logistic Regression Technique for Optimizing Adaptive Reuse of Historical Castles. *Int. J. Neutrosophic Sci.* 2023, 21(3), 56–??. <https://doi.org/10.54216/IJNS.210305>.
- [12] Patiño, A.; Guevara, D.; Molina, S. Diagnosis of the Ecuadorian penitentiary system: between structural crisis and institutional inefficiency. *Andean J. Legal Stud.* 2023, 18(2), 112–129. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fqgkz>.
- [13] Cruz Piza, I.A.; Troya Terranova, K.T.; Maldonado Manzano, R.L. Empleo de la neutrosofía en el análisis de la crisis del sistema penitenciario en el Ecuador y su incidencia en los derechos humanos fundamentales. *Neutrosophic Comput. Mach. Learn.* 2023, 28, 223–230. <https://zenodo.org/record/8408648>.
- [14] Prison massacre cases 2021–2022. *Recimundo* 2022, 6(3), 222–233.
- [15] Smarandache, F. Refined n-valued neutrosophic logic and its applications to physics. In *Collected Papers. Volume X: On Neutrosophics, Plithogenics, Hypersoft Sets, Hypergraphs, and Other Topics*; 2022; p. 170.
- [16] Vázquez, M.L.; Torres, L.C. Integrating neutrosophic numbers in regression analysis for enhancing predictive modeling through uncertainty representation. *Plithogenic Log. Comput.* 2024, 1, 120–126.
- [17] Salama, A.A.; Khalid, H.E.; Essa, A.K.; Ahmed, N.M. A Natural Language Processing Environment for Rule-Based Decision Making with Neutrosophic Logic to Manage Uncertainty and Ambiguity. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2025, 82(1), 44.
- [18] Campaña-Muñoz, L.C.; Sánchez Ramos, H.S.; Cabrera Granda, J.R. Use of neutrosophy for the analysis of the social reintegration factors of released prisoners in Ecuador. *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.* 2019, 26(1), 22.

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